

IMPORTANCE OF COOPERATIVE TEACHING IN MULTI-AGED GROUPS

Akhmedova Feruza Jabborali qizi

Angren University

fakhmedova1902@gmail.com

Khakimova Khosiyat Jurayevna

Angren University

hakimovaxosiyat@gmail.com

Tolipova Gulfiya Fayzulla qizi

Angren University

tolipvagulfiya@gmail.com

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10215515>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th November 2023

Accepted: 27th November 2023

Online: 28th November 2023

KEY WORDS

Cooperative learning, learner-centered approach, teacher-centered approach, multi-age grouping, socio-emotional development, informal learning groups, formal learning groups, cooperative base groups, cognitive and meta-cognitive skills, communicative language coaching.

ABSTRACT

The main goal of the article makes up our minds the effectiveness and advantages of cooperative learning as teaching method of multi-aged students.

Teaching foreign languages in academic establishments brings out some responsibilities and effective advantages to the academic system of our country wherever each chance is accessible for all ages. The high demand for learning English is taken into thought and each facilities area unit supplied with the assistance of recent technologies and strategies. Moreover, the perception from that analysis was mentioned with benefits of exploitation cooperative learning strategies in rising potency of learning foreign languages. The cooperative learning strategy promotes students' active learning by making simulated real-life language atmosphere. With the implementation of cooperative learning within the foreign instruction, students' area supplied with loads of opportunities to participate, experience, move and join forces in foreign acquisition within the cooperative cluster, students work along, interacting face to face with the identical goal of learning, also as aiding one another (Borich, 2007).

One of the most important functions of the paper is to come back up with the thought for effectively coping with approaches of teaching English to totally different aged students and to recommend exploitation numerous strategies in numerous categories joined of the effective thanks to come through the goal. As mentioned, the present teaching strategies and

approaches' main purpose is to involve learners into learning English actively. As a result, all the teaching is learner-centered rather than teacher-centered. This article would be very useful for not only English teachers at schools, but also teachers who work with mixed classes in other educational centers.

The importance of implementing cooperative learning strategies among multi-aged groups is becoming a big issue that must be solved, since new educational institutions are being established. For instance, professional schools, which provide learners with 5th degree, and educational centers are taking a significant role in our country. Both educational institutions do not have age limit for learners, however, teaching them in a proper way and using effective methods are in target now. Using traditional methods not always gives us better results, instead, addressing to modern methodology and adjusting it to the current situation seems to be the reasonable way to overcome emerging language gaps.

Past studies are primarily focused on the importance of grouping in cooperative learning and implementation the very method among seniors. Grouping, on the other hand, is considered to be one of the basic points. Research data indicates that students selected grouping is more preferred way, meaning that students are better to choose their partners or groups themselves. According to Wichadee and Orawiwatnakul (2012) the effect of cooperative language learning was not only improving learners' language skills, but also creates a supportive learning environment among students.

In history of the world, education was available only for those who could afford it. However, the need to educate massive illiterate population gained special attention of the government and the need to provide people with proper classrooms became another big issue. The multi-age grouping concept was introduced by Horace Mann in midcenturies became the solution of many problems. By 2000s, this new approach had been the target of researchers.

Employing a multiage technique to coaching college students builds on the belief that it may be individualized to fulfill the developmental desires of college students. Several research have seemed into the connection among multiage grouping and educational success. Inconsistent effects were discovered in studies reviews. Some researches declare that scholars in multiage school rooms do higher on standardized success assessments. Inconsistencies in studies consequences, in line with Veenman (1995), can be associated with an ambiguous idea of multiage schooling. Other researchers blame ambiguous studies consequences on a loss of element in records processing and inadequate controls for variations among experimental and manage circumstances, notwithstanding the reality that experimental research have to be designed to account for those discrepancies. In different cases, the compelled venture of each college students and instructors to multiage school rooms may despite, variations in research findings, studies that show significant achievement outcomes for pupils in multiage classrooms above single-age schools show linguistic advances. Both high- and low-ability pupils have benefited from the program. Long-term research has demonstrated that the benefits of multiage classrooms grow as students remain in multiage classes for extended periods of time. In the academic world, consistent reports across research of specific benefits of multiage grouping in the field of socio-emotional development back up the advantages. When compared to peers in typical graded classrooms,

students in multiage classrooms have more positive views toward school, more leadership abilities, higher self-esteem, and increased pro-social and fewer aggressive behaviors. These characteristics have been found to have a positive impact on achievement outcomes in both traditional and multiage classes. The inconsistent effects in the academic arena are surprising, given the consistent favorable benefits of multiage grouping in the socio-emotional realm. The adoption of a developmentally appropriate strategy to teaching, such as teaming, cooperative group work, integrated curriculum, and encouragement of student interactions, is a consistent component in studies that indicate higher achievement outcomes for multiage students above same-age students. The use of developmentally appropriate teaching approaches in creating favorable achievement outcomes is supported by research. Furthermore, a large amount of evidence supports the use of cooperative educational efforts over competitive or individualistic educational efforts. Slavin's research, on the other hand, shows that peer interaction does not improve learning in and of itself. Learning enhancement, on the other hand, is dependent on how the teacher directs such encounters.

When figuring out if cooperative learning is a technique suitable on your lesson, it's critical to recognize the diverse kinds. There are 3 typically identified styles of cooperative learning: informal learning groups, formal learning groups and cooperative base groups. Each type has its own cause and application.

Informal Learning Groups. These are informal short-term meetings with little structure. They usually consist of exercises in which students look to their neighbors for a few minutes to discuss topics and concepts. Informal groups are usually small and consist of 2-3 people. For rapid activities such as comprehension testing, brainstorming, rapid problem solving, summarization, and reviews, it is best to use informal research groups. These groups are a great way to divide a lecture by allowing students to discuss concepts with colleagues for a few minutes. It can be summarized as a teaching material on the go. Informal groups are especially useful for breaking the story into smaller chunks with group activities in between. This strategy reduces lecture time, but increases the amount of material held by students and the convenience of interaction.

Formal Learning Groups. Formal studying corporations are given an undertaking or challenge and should end it collectively. The maximum not unusual place utility of cooperative studying is on this form of group. Members of a set may go on long-time period tasks collectively for numerous weeks. These are the corporations wherein college students look at and exercise the various approaches for cooperating with one another. The instructor has hooked up a clean shape for those corporations, which incorporates undertaking and behavior standards. Depending at the undertaking, formal studying corporations is probably heterogeneous or homogeneous. Most corporations of 3 to 4 human beings' paintings well; any greater than 5 individuals can turn out to be unproductive. Formal studying corporations may be used within side the study room to finish a challenge, remedy a chain of tasks, revise for a test, or write a report.

Cooperative base group. These groups differ from the previous two groups in that the basic co-operative group is a long-term, stable group that lasts for at least a year and is made up of people with different skills and perspectives. increase. The basic group should last at least one semester, but can last up to several years. Because these are long-term efforts, these

groups tend to be more than just academic problem-solving groups. Community members often become mutual personal support systems, building relationships and trust during the collaborative learning process. The purpose of a collaborative grassroots group is for members to fulfill their responsibilities among their peers and support each other by learning together. They provide a situation where students can support each other in science and other aspects of life. Group members make sure that everyone is doing their job and are responsible for contributing to each other. By implementing collaborative basic groups in such a way that students meet regularly during learning to solve collaborative learning tasks, students develop in a scientifically developed, cognitively and socially sound way. We can provide the permanent support and supervision you need to do.

It is permissible to use multiple types of groups at the same time. For example, you can assign a formal research group to a project, but use an informal group during a lesson where the formal group is not linked. If there are classes that are difficult to collaborate with, students may need many opportunities to practice the collaboration. Start and move towards a more formal co-learning situation.

According to Slavin (1983) strategies of cooperative studying traditionally include number one additives: a cooperative incentive shape (Arend's definition) and a cooperative undertaking shape. Cooperative incentive shape is what maximum theorists imply after they consult with cooperation. Slavin persevered that the important function of a cooperative incentive shape is that or extra people are interdependence for a praise they may proportion if they're successful. He illustrated, for example, if 3 human beings journeying in a vehicle assist push the auto out of the mud, they all gain from every other's efforts (via way of means of being capable of maintain the trip). All may be rewarded or none of them may be, relying on whether or not they prevail or now no longer. While cooperative undertaking systems are conditions wherein or extra people are allowed, encouraged, or required to paintings collectively on a few tasks, coordinating their efforts to finish the undertaking. Students' paintings cooperative tasks, however the undertaking themselves are wonderful every other. In one undertaking, for instance, one pupil might also additionally work to gather and pick dialogue materials, each other lead dialogue, the rests are likely a notary, front-instructor presenter, and so on. Slavin explained: For example, participants to an edited quantity are beneath a cooperative incentive shape (all of them gain if the book does nicely even though they by no means meet or communicate with each other (i.e., they're now no longer beneath a cooperative undertaking shape)⁵. As to remind, intention shape is the quantity of interdependences (individualistic, competitive, and cooperative) required to college students whilst operating collectively. Those 3 additives undergo a few strategies which accommodate coaching studying procedure primarily based totally on instructors and college students need. Three maximum famous and normally used strategies till now are Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD), Jigsaw, and Group Investigation (GI). As to know, a technique is the important cognizance of an approach. The originators of a technique have arrived at selections approximately varieties of activities, roles of instructors and learners, the forms of cloth to be able to be helpful, and a few versions of syllabus organization. Methods encompass diverse approaches and strategies

Currently, co-operative education up to foreign language instruction is being conducted in the classroom. Collaborative proficiency and English as a second or foreign language in the classroom is a great integration (Kagan, 2001). There is research development focused primarily on the impact and effectiveness of collaborative mastering in classroom foreign language training. According to Crandall (1999), collaborative language skills have the wonderful elements of learning a language, motivating, relieving tension, stimulating motivation, selling self-esteem, and supporting outstanding proficiency.

The collaborative learning method promotes active learning of students through the development of a realistic language environment. By conducting collaborative learning within the framework of foreign language coaching, students are provided with additional opportunities for participation, experience, interaction and cooperation in foreign language learning. At cooperating institutions, college students have the same goal of drawing together, interacting face-to-face, mastering and supporting each other (Borich, 2007). Collaborative learning is probably the ideal way to achieve this goal, as language teachers need to create a vibrant mastering ecosystem where college children study on their own with many blessings. Suwantarabip and Wichadee (2010) tested the effectiveness of co-learning to relieve tensions in learning a foreign language and examined its impact on language proficiency assessment of 40 college students. It was found that the tensions of college students in learning foreign languages were dramatically alleviated after they learned the joint learning technique. In addition, there was a growing desire for joint learning among all university students. In a collaborative language proficiency environment, institutional coaching has become a learner-centric approach, and organizations have been designed so that each member does their job to achieve their goals. They argued that previous studies have shown that the effects of collaborative language acquisition are no longer the best language skills for advanced learners, but they also create a supportive environment for proficiency. Their research recommends that, despite the great effects of collaborative teaching techniques, it is necessary to acquire some knowledge for teaching control modes in order to avoid problems that actually occur in the end. This method enhances basic social skills, improves communication skills, presents a great version for lifelong learning, and brings additional doctrinal enrichment to all members of the institution. It is believed to promote a great environment for mastering.⁴ Constructivist approaches, including collaborative teaching enable the enhancement of cognitive and meta-cognitive skills needed to build real-world knowledge. Nevertheless, collaborative mastering is a powerful approach to dealing with multiple intelligences.

Due to the evolving perception of communicative language coaching, some blessings of collaborative teaching in the context of foreign language school spaces have been noted. Crandall (1999) also contributes to the effectiveness of collaborative language skills by relieving student tensions, promoting great attitudes towards language skills, and increasing self-esteem. A flexible learning ecosystem formed by cooperation rather than opposition is also expected to increase the degree of autonomy of college students.

Considering the disadvantages of cooperative learning, not all college students can participate in co-learning in a similar manner and are most conscientious. In addition, Pica (1994) noticed that in foreign language systems if teachers are not involved, students tend to

use their native language. Richards and Rodgers (2001) also found that the cooperative command of the place puts another burden on teachers who may not be able to cope well with changes in position within the classroom.

The literature reviews provided above reviewed teaching studies and focused on the fundamental additions essential to their effective implementation: great interdependence, personality obligations, and institutional processing.

As a conclusion we can say that, almost every student put forward that through communication, they become aware of individual differences. They realize that there is not only one way in the process of solution to a problem. This lead them trusting each other in the group as most of them are at the same side of this idea. As a result, of this they understand that moving together would bring success to all of them. On the way to the solution they discuss in groups, suggest ideas, find what is wrong and at the end they develop their higher order thinking skills. Most think that they learn the way of cooperation through showing respect to each other's thoughts while studying on the common task. They indicate that this is also a way of learning to be tolerant. By this way, they grow the feeling of respect towards both themselves and the others.

Students know that when the group has a common task to achieve, the reward is also common. Because of this, the members encourage each other to reach the goal and this naturally motivates the group members. As another result of motivation, it can be said that students grow positive attitude towards school, learning and the class. It is obvious that most students prefer studying in cooperative learning environments rather than working individually in case doing the distribution of task carefully, arranging the groups sensibly to avoid giving harm to creativity, sociability and motivation of the students.

The classroom often offers a student's first experiences practicing most life skills. Teachers should deliberately create opportunities for students to cooperate with each other, share responsibilities, solve problems, and control conflict. These opportunities can be found in cooperative learning, which differs from individualistic or traditional learning where students work independently, sometimes even against each other. Cooperative learning activities require students to work together in small groups to complete a project or activity, operating as a team to help each other succeed. Cooperative learning, of course, teaches a number of social and emotional skills, but it also gives students the opportunity to learn from each other. Studies show that peer learning in which students explain concepts and ideas to each other has the potential to improve comprehension considerably.

In short, cooperative learning produces critical experiences that other learning structures cannot. The following skills that are developed through regular and effective cooperative learning are just a few of many. Students who work together as a team share a common goal: a successful project. This can only be achieved through the combined efforts of the whole group. The ability to work as a team towards a common goal is an invaluable quality to have in the real world, especially for careers.

It takes time, patience, and tenacity to enable collaborative learning. The more you learn about cooperative learning and practice your skills, the better you will get results and the more benefits. All collaborative learning activities help students practice working in teams. "Teams should be able to act with the same determination and concentration as motivated

individuals," said Bill Gates, co-founder of Microsoft. The Team Building Exercise teaches students to trust each other to achieve together more than is possible in other ways.

References:

1. Borich, G. D. (2007). *"Effective teaching methods"* Research –based practice. Ohio: Pearson Education Inc
2. Crandall, J. A. (1999). *Cooperative language learning and affective factors*. In Arnold, J. (ed.) *Affective factors in language learning*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 226-245.
3. Jack C. Richards and Theodore S. Rodgers (2001) *"Approaches and Methods in Language teaching"* Cambridge University Press 2001.
4. Kagan (2001) *"Cooperative Learning Model: The Bridge to Foreign Language Learning in the Third Millennium"*. 2012 Academy Publisher
5. T. Pica (1994) *Research on Negotiation: What Does It Reveal about Second Language Learning Conditions, Processes, and Outcomes?* DOI: 10.1111/J.1467-1770.1994.TB01115.XCorpus ID: 143841011
6. Slavin, R. E. (1983). *Cooperative learning*. New York, NY: Longman.
7. Suwantarathip, O., & Wichadee, S. (2010). *The Impacts Of Cooperative Learning On Anxiety And Proficiency In An EFL Class*. *Journal of College Teaching & Learning (TLC)*, 7(11).
8. Veenman (1995) *Cognitive and Non-cognitive Effects of Multi-grade and Multi-Age Classes: A Best-Evidence Synthesis*.
9. Wichadee S. & Orawiwatnakul W. (2012). *Cooperative Language Learning: Increasing Opportunities for Learning In Teams*. *Journal of College Teaching and Learning*. Vol. 9 (2). Bangkok University, Thailand.